

Handout Didactic Lesson Plan - Basic version

Timing	Learning Outcomes	Content	Didactic Method	Media	Evaluation Method

Handout Didactic Lesson Plan - Detailed version

Timing & Phase	Learning Outcomes & Teaching aims	Content & Terminology	Didactic Method & Tasks	Media & Material	Evaluation Method & Tasks

Handout Didactic Lesson Plan - Detailed version - Explanation & references

Overall didactic principles

Constructive Alignment - Reference Biggs, J.: Constructive Alignment <https://www.johnbiggs.com.au/academic/constructive-alignment/>

Motivational Design - Reference Keller, J. M. (2009): Motivational Design for Learning and Performance: The ARCS Model Approach. Springer Science & Business Media, New York, USA, p. 45, Table 3.1, https://books.google.de/books?id=HRCQIzZMwHsC&pg=PA43&hl=de&source=gbs_toc_r&cad=3#v=onepage&q&f=false

	Timing & Phase	Learning Outcomes (L.O.s) & Teaching aims	Content & Terminology	Didactic Method & Tasks	Media & Material	Evaluation Method & Tasks
Explanation & Advice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Write down how here many minutes you spent on each sequence -Structure lessons in a realistic way, imply time for the unexpected -Plan various phases -After max 20 min. input, give time for processing, transfer, questions, in online teaching before 20 minutes 	<p><u>Learning Outcomes</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Find out which L.O. should be reached -Define further L.O.s -Use verbs + content for writing L.O.s -Communicate L.O.s to students in all lessons f. orientation <p><u>Teaching aims</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Write down what you intend to do to reach L. O.s, see sample lesson plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reduce input to promote student's understanding -Keep content accurate & expandable and select "Musts" & "Mights" -Write & explain vocabulary/terms (field-/method-related) that students might not know -Provide definitions, explanations, or let students write these, e.g. in a glossary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Select overall did. strategy suitable for intended L.O.s -Choose activating teaching- & learning methods -Imply methods that allow processing -Prepare the tasks for students & write these down, e.g. to copy into chat in online-teaching or on paper/board -Check outcomes of learning activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Use various media to visualize input & content -Create materials that are clear in task & promote single- & group work -Prepare visualization material -Follow principles of visualization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Select method/s that show students' L.O.s -Imply methods for --feedback from you --and from students to students --from students to you -Choose short evaluation methods every lesson -Prepare the tasks for evaluation for students & write these down, e.g. to copy into chat in online-teaching or on paper/board
Relevant didactic principles	<u>Phase Orientation</u>	<u>Learning Outcome orientation</u> according to Constructive Alignment	<u>Didactic reduction</u> <u>Motivational Design</u>	<u>Motivational Design</u> <u>Learner orientation & activation</u>	<u>Visualization principles</u>	<u>Continuous assessment</u> <u>Formative evaluation</u>

Relevant didactic principles - References & Links for further study (06.01.2022)

Phase Orientation

Phase-sequencing in learning processes

Phase	Task
Introductory phase	Introduction/Warm-up
Elaboration	Acquisition of new knowledge and skills
Processing	Application of and practice of approaching new knowledge
Concluding phase	Evaluation and ensuring transfer; transition to new learning cycles

Translated and extended by ©Alexandra Bergedick: Tab. C 2.9-1 Phasenfolge in Lernprozessen -Szczyrba, B./Wildt, J. (2005): Vom akademischen Viertel zur methodisch regulierten Anwärmphase - Anfangssituationen in Lehrveranstaltungen. In: B. Behrendt/Voss, H.-P./Wildt, J. (Hrsg.): Neues Handbuch Hochschullehre. Raabe-Verlag: Berlin, C 2.9, p.4.

Learning Outcome Orientation / Constructive Alignment

See Handout & Worksheet Constructive Alignment

See Handouts & Worksheet Defining & Writing Learning Outcomes and Bloom's Taxonomy

Motivational Design

See Handout Motivational Design for further study

Didactic reduction

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Extreme-Didactic-Reduction-in-Computational-Futschek/27afc88739659e53cbfeba962d65d60199cbc879>

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/A-theoretical-model-of-the-causal-map_fig1_311977219

https://www.wbv.de/fileadmin/webshop/pdf/Impulsvortrag_Martin-Lehner.pdf

-Stary, J. (2004). Das didaktische Kernproblem. Verfahren und Kriterien der didaktischen Reduktion. In: Berendt, B./ Voss, H.-P./ Wildt, J.

(Hrsg)(2004): Neues Handbuch Hochschullehre. Raabe-Verlag: Bonn, A 1.2. NHHL 1 12 04 05

-Brinker, T./Schumacher, E.-M. (2014): Befähigen statt belehren. Neue Lehr- und Lernkultur an Hochschulen. Lehrkit für Hochschuldozierende: Arbeitsbuch und 66 Methodenkarten. Hep-Verlag: Bern.

Learner orientation & -activation

<https://www.case-ka.eu/index.html%3Fp=2740.html>

See Unit 2 & 4

Visualization Principles

You can find a lot of information on how to effectively visualize what you want to teach & students to learn in an internet search.

Continuous assessment & formative evaluation

See Unit 6

More examples for lesson plans

Sample lesson plans

- <https://oregonstate.app.box.com/s/99va312r2mblxijv96jiipyynyva5n76>
- <https://www.class-templates.com/lesson-plan-format.html>
- <https://www.template.net/business/plan-templates/higher-education-lesson-plan/>
- <https://en.islcollective.com/english-esl-worksheets/material-type/teaching-videos/perspectives-upper-intermediate-lesson-plans/120310>
- <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/view/37468343/example-first-day-lesson-plan>
- <https://osu-wams-blogs-uploads.s3.amazonaws.com/blogs.dir/1441/files/2020/06/Lesson-Plan-Template-Image.jpg>